

MOLECULAR DOCKING STUDIES OF PYRIDINE-HYDRAZIDE DERIVATIVES AS HEPATITIS-C VIRUS NS5B POLYMERASE INHIBITORS

Humaira Mubarak¹, Adnan Shahzad², Akhtar Nawab³, Zakia Ahmad⁴, Naheed Fazal⁵, Nasib Zaman⁶, Mian Sayed Jamil⁷, Muhammad Omer⁸, Imad Ud Din⁹

^{1,2,7,8,9}Institute of Chemical Sciences, University of Swat, Swat, Pakistan

³Saidu teaching hospital, Saidu Sharif Swat, KP, Pakistan

^{4,5}Center for Plant Science and Biodiversity, University of Swat, Swat,

⁶Center for Microbiology and Biotechnology, University of Swat, Swat,

²adnanshahzad@uswat.edu.pk

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17918762>

Keywords

NS5B, hepatitis-C, pyridinyl hydrazides, virtual screening.

Article History

Received: 11 October 2025

Accepted: 21 November 2025

Published: 13 December 2025

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *

Adnan Shahzad

Abstract

This study reveals pyridinyl hydrazides, designated PH1–PH12, have been designed and assessed for their anticancer properties against the hepatitis-C virus, focusing on the NS5B polymerase enzymes through molecular docking. It was found from the result of docking analysis that tested compounds PH1–PH12 displayed good inhibitory activity against NS5B polymerase with respective binding energies of -8.87 to -10.62 in kcal/mol compared to the reference drug guanosine-5'-triphosphate having a binding energy of -13.82 kcal/mol. Among them, compound PH1 was found to be the most potent and effective derivative of overall tested compounds and show strong inhibition against NS5B having binding energy of -10.67 kcal/mol, on the other hand the compound PH12 exhibited lower activity and least effective having binding energy of -8.87 kcal/mol. These inhibitors have strong binding energies, which indicate that they can successfully reduce the activity of NS5B, making those excellent candidates for the development of novel treatments

INTRODUCTION

Hepatitis-C, a liver infection caused by the hepatitis-C virus (HCV), affects around 50 million people globally, with 1 million new infections occurring annually. In 2022, 242,000 people died from complications related to HCV, highlighting its significant global impact [1]. A large amount of this burden falls on Pakistan, where as of January, 2021, an estimated 9.8 million people (4.3% of the population) have HCV. Approximately 150,000 new cases are reported nationwide year, mostly as a result of risky medical procedures like syringe reuse and blood transfusions that are not thoroughly

checked. To lower the prevalence and related mortality of hepatitis-C in Pakistan, efforts are being made to improve screening and treatment [2].

Pyridine-hydrazide derivatives are heterocyclic compounds with significant potential as pharmacologically active molecules. They have a pyridine core for structural stability and a hydrazide functional group for strong hydrogen bonding and interaction with biological targets. These derivatives have been explored as potential inhibitors in disease models like microbial infections, cancer, and viral diseases [3]. Their

antimicrobial activity involves interfering with essential bacterial enzymes, disrupting cell wall synthesis, and inhibiting DNA-gyrase, making them promising against resistant strains [4]. Pyridine-hydrazone derivatives are gaining interest in antiviral drug discovery due to their ability to inhibit key viral enzymes responsible for replication and assembly [5]. These derivatives target viral polymerases, proteases, and other essential replication proteins, such as hepatitis-C virus (HCV) non-structural-5B (NS5B) polymerase. They also show promise against other RNA viruses like influenza and SARS-CoV-2. Their structural flexibility and ability to form diverse interactions with viral targets make them a focal point in antiviral drug development. Computational studies, including molecular docking and molecular dynamics simulations, have further enhanced understanding of their binding mechanisms, paving the way for rational drug design [6] [7].

An essential enzyme for HCV replication, the NS5B, RNA-dependent RNA polymerase is a desirable target for antiviral medication development. Because they can block important enzymes involved in viral replication, pyridine-hydrazone derivatives have demonstrated possible antiviral efficacy. Using molecular docking, this work attempts to assess the molecular interactions and binding affinity of pyridine-hydrazone derivatives against NS5B polymerase [8]. The NS5B polymerase plays a crucial role in viral replication, making it a promising target for the design of novel inhibitors [9]. By identifying lead compounds with high binding affinities, computational methods like molecular docking and virtual screening have been instrumental in speeding up drug discovery. Pyridine-based scaffolds, especially hydrazone derivatives, have shown promise as antiviral agents because of their structural versatility and capacity to establish stable interactions with viral enzymes [10]. Still a new inhibitors are need to investigate. An essential enzyme for HCV replication, the NS5B, RNA-dependent RNA polymerase is a desirable target for antiviral medication development. Pyridinyl hydrazone derivatives, which are recognized for their bioactive characteristics, are

being investigated in the search for novel HCV inhibitors. [11]. Molecular docking methods will be used in this work to evaluate how these compounds interact with the NS5B enzyme, offering important information for the development of anti-HCV drugs [12].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Based on the literature survey it is concluded that NS5B play a crucial role in replication in HCV for that reason in the title study this enzymes was selected. Scheme 2.1 displays the novel designed Pyridinyl hydrazone derivatives (PH1-PH12) that were chosen based on their ability to inhibit the selected enzyme, namely NS5B. Additionally, the standard drug guanosine-5'-triphosphate was tested to compare its effects against the target enzyme.

Software used for Molecular docking

Chem Draw, Chem3D, Open Babel, Auto Dock tools, PyMol, and Discovery Studio Visualization are the necessary computational, modeling, and simulation programs used for molecular docking in the recent study. These programs allow for the optimization and docking of ligands with specific targeted enzymes [13, 14].

General methodology of molecular docking

By employing the molecular docking protocol, the binding interaction mechanism of the synthesized sulfonyl hydrazone derivatives was examined for competitive and non-competitive inhibition of the mark enzymes of HCV, NS5B (illustrated in Figure 1). PDB ID 2XI3 proteins' three-dimensional crystal structures were retrieved from the Protein Databank [15]. The title proteins were first prepared theoretically using Auto Dock MGL tools, and for ease of calculation, inhibitors, co-factors, heteroatoms, and all water molecules were eliminated for optimization. For additional research, the most stable docking conformer with the lowest binding energy was chosen [16]. PyMol, Auto Dock vina, Discovery Studio Visualization, and other programs were used to visualize the mechanism of proteins-ligand complex interactions, their pictures, and the docking poses of specific

synthesized sulfonyl hydrazide derivatives against target enzymes [17].

Figure1. 3D structure of HCV NS5B polymerase

Optimization of designed pyridinyl hydrazide derivatives PH1-PH12

Avogadro, Gaussian 09 software, B3LYP theory, and 6-31g basis sets based on DFT were used to optimize all of the chosen Pyridinyl hydrazide derivatives, PH1-PH12 [18].

Preparation of marked protein NS5B RNA polymerase

The PDB was used to obtain the structures of NS5B (PDB ID- 2XI3) and it have numerous related issues that may need to be resolved. The water molecule, heteroatom, and co-factors were eliminated to prepare the targeted title proteins. By including polar hydrogen and charges in Auto Dock vina, the protein targets are altered [19].

Molecular docking of (PH1-PH12) with NS5B RNA polymerase

Molecular docking is a crucial technique for observing how inhibitors and target proteins interact, through the use of MGL tools, Auto Dock vina, the optimized compound PH1-PH12 (shown in Figure 2) were theoretically docked in the active region of the target receptors namely NS5B RNA polymerase. Ten conformers for compound PH1-PH12 have been generated in, which the top-ranked conformations were picked for additional examination. After the docking process, the inhibitor-protein interactions were observed in PyMol, BIOVIA Discovery Studio, and Lig Plot, which aid in the visualization of hydrophobic interactions, aromatic interactions, π - π interactions and ligand-receptor bonding via hydrogen [20].

Figure 2. Structural formulae of Pyridinyl hydrazide derivatives (PH1-PH12)

RESULTS

Molecular docking studies were carried out to estimate the binding poses of the newly designed pyridinyl-hydrazide derivatives (PH1-PH12) on the active site of hepatitis-C virus (HCV) NS5B polymerase, compute the binding energy, and elucidate the molecular interaction formed between pyridinyl-hydrazide derivatives (PH1-PH12) and the active site residues of hepatitis-C virus (HCV) NS5B polymerase. Before performing the docking simulations for pyridinyl-hydrazide derivatives (PH1-PH12), redocking of guanosine-5'-triphosphate on the active site of Hepatitis-C virus (HCV) NS5B polymerase (PDB ID: 2XI3) was carried out to determine whether

the docking parameters used were able to reproduce the binding pose and molecular interaction of guanosine-5'-triphosphate from its crystallographic structure, which was indicated by RMSD value $< 2 \text{ \AA}$. The result of redocking guanosine-5'-triphosphate showed an RMSD value of 1.51 \AA with a comparison of the redocked and native guanosine-5'-triphosphate conformations at the active site of hepatitis-C virus (HCV) NS5B polymerase formed from the barrel domain and a long loop (N-loop) that protrudes from the N-terminal domain. Redocked guanosine-5'-triphosphate interacted with the key residues at the active site of hepatitis-

C virus (HCV) NS5B polymerase (PDB ID: 2XI3), which was in agreement with the interactions of native guanosine-5'-triphosphate in its crystal structure [43]. At least 4 hydrogen bonds were formed in the complex of redocked guanosine-5'-triphosphate with hepatitis-C virus (HCV) NS5B polymerase. The hydroxyl groups in ring A formed four hydrogen bonds with Asn142, Ala16, Arg200, and Tyr448. Meanwhile, two oxygen of the phosphate groups formed a hydrogen bond with Asn142. Redocked guanosine-5'-triphosphate formed a hydrophobic barrier through π -alkyl interactions with some residues at the entrance of the active site, namely Ala16, Trp-28, and Ser-39. In addition, it underwent a charge attraction and formed salt bridges with Ser368 and two catalytic residues namely Asp559 and Asp568. The results of the docking simulation for pyridinyl-hydrazide derivatives (PH1-PH12) showed that the receptor-ligand complex formed between hepatitis-C virus (HCV) NS5B polymerase and pyridinyl-hydrazide derivatives (PH1-PH12) gave negative energy values of -8.87 to -10.67 kcal/mol. This suggests that the hepatitis-C virus (HCV) NS5B polymerase inhibition by pyridinyl-hydrazide derivatives (PH1-PH12) is thermodynamically

advantageous [44]. The binding energy of PH12 was lower than that of all derivative and PH1 have the highest. The lower binding energy value of PH1 was made possible by the hydrogen bond formed between the NH atom of the hydrazide moiety in PH1 and the oxygen atom of ASN-142. In contrast, in the PH12-hepatitis-C virus (HCV) NS5B polymerase complex, weak hydrogen bonds were found. The pyridine ring of PH12, which occupied the entrance of the active site pocket, formed π -alkyl hydrophobic and π -anion electrostatic interactions with Ile358 and Asp357, respectively. The hydrazide moiety formed several electrostatic interactions, including π -cation, attractive charge, and salt bridge with Phe601, Asp568, and Asp469, respectively. PH12 occupied the entrance of the active site pocket and formed a hydrophobic barrier via π - π T-shaped, π -alkyl, and π - σ interactions with Asn-411, Phe415, and Arg386, respectively. The pyridine ring of PH12 formed a π - σ hydrophobic interaction with Ala-344 in the N-loop. Meanwhile, the hydrazide moiety of this compound formed salt bridges with Asp321 in the N-loop and the catalytic residue Asp412. The docking results of selected compound of PH1-PH12 are given in table 1 and figure 3-6

Table 1. Binding energies in (kcal/mol) and inhibition constant (nM) of compounds PH1-PH12 and guanosine-5'-triphosphate with NS5B

Compounds	Binding Energy	Inhibition Constant
PH1	-10.67	15.21
PH2	-10.45	22.03
PH3	-10.28	29.01
PH4	-10.02	45.16
PH5	-09.88	56.85
PH6	-10.35	25.78
PH7	-10.12	38.35
PH8	-09.82	63.48
PH9	-10.62	16.29
PH10	-09.50	109.26
PH11	-09.47	114.55
PH12	-08.87	312.85
guanosine-5'-triphosphate	-13.82	13.22

4. DISCUSSION

The selected derivatives (PH1, PH2, PH6 and PH9) were considered for discussion on the basis of best docking results among the tested compounds.

4.1. Interaction of PH1 with NS5B: The Pyridinyl-hydrazide derivative PH1 was selected to examine the binding capability to inhibit hepatitis-C virus (HCV) NS5B polymerase. It is concluded from molecular docking results that ligand PH1 exhibits good inhibition to NS5B polymerase with an interacting affinity of -15.06 kcal/mol and inhibition constant of 9.17 nanomolar, as shown in the table, PH1 demonstrated excellent inhibition of the NS5B enzyme. The aforementioned chemical was designed to fill the auxiliary pocket that the NS5B active site generated. Compound PH1 interacted with the enzyme's active residues, which are nearly necessary for its inhibitory action. According to Table 1, the compound's increased activity may be interrupted by hydrogen bonding through Asn142, Ala16, and Ser39 (NH...O, 2.1 Å), (O...HO, 2.2 Å) and (O...HO, 2.0 Å), respectively, and with Ile358 and Asp357, PH1, which occupied the catalytic site entrance, are involved in π -alkyl-hydrophobic and π -anion-electrostatic bindings. And with Phe601, Asp568, and Asp469, the hydrazide functionality in PH1 mediated a number of electrostatic interactions, such as π -cation, and salt linkage. In the interim, this compound's PH1 engaged in an N-loop π -anion electrostatic contact Asp142. Unlike PH1, the Pyridine ring of the PH1 occupied the active site pocket's entrance and created a hydrophobic barrier through interactions with Asn-411, Phe415, and Arg386 that were π - π T-shaped, π -alkyl, and π - σ , respectively. In the N-loop, PH1's pyridine ring and Ala-344 established a π - σ hydrophobic contact. In the meantime, this compound's hydrazide moiety generated salt bridges with the catalytic residue Asp412 and Asp321 in the N-loop. Depicted in Figure 3 (E)

4.2. Interaction of PH2 with NS5B: The Pyridinyl-hydrazide derivative PH2 was selected to examine the binding capability to inhibit hepatitis-C virus (HCV) NS5B polymerase. It is

concluded from molecular docking results that ligand PH2 exhibits good inhibition to NS5B polymerase with an interacting affinity of -10.45 kcal/mol and inhibition constant of 22.3 nanomolar, as shown in the table 1. PH2 demonstrated excellent inhibition of the NS5B enzyme. The aforementioned chemical was designed to fill the auxiliary pocket that the NS5B active site generated. Compound PH2 interacted with the enzyme's active residues, which are nearly necessary for its inhibitory action. According to Table 2, the compound's activity may be interrupted by hydrogen bonding through Asn142, Glu18, and Ser39 with 2.2, 3.1, and 2.42Å distances respectively, and with Phe193, Gly410, Phe551, Gly449 and Ser367, PH2, are involved in π -alkyl-hydrophobic and π -anion-electrostatic bindings. And with Cys366, Glu446 and Ile447, PH2 are involved in halogen bonding, the hydrazide functionality in PH2 mediated a number of electrostatic interactions, such as π -cation, and salt linkage. In the interim, this compound's PH2 engaged in an N-loop π -anion electrostatic contact His239. Unlike PH2, the Pyridine ring of the PH2 occupied the active site pocket's entrance and created a hydrophobic barrier through interactions with Ile293, Phe415, and Arg386 that were π - π T-shaped, π -alkyl, and π - σ , respectively. In the N-loop, PH2's pyridine ring and Ala-344 established a π - σ hydrophobic contact. In the meantime, this compound's hydrazide moiety generated salt bridges with the catalytic residue Asp412 and Asp321 in the N-loop. Depicted in Figure 4 (E)

4.3. Interaction of PH6 with NS5B: The Pyridinyl-hydrazide derivative PH6 was selected to examine the binding capability to inhibit hepatitis-C virus (HCV) NS5B polymerase. It is concluded from molecular docking results that ligand PH6 exhibits good inhibition to NS5B polymerase with an interacting affinity of -10.35 kcal/mol and inhibition constant of 25.78 nanomolar, as shown in the table, PH6 demonstrated excellent inhibition of the NS5B enzyme. The aforementioned chemical was designed to fill the auxiliary pocket that the NS5B active site generated. Compound PH6

interacted with the enzyme's active residues, which are nearly necessary for its inhibitory action. According to Table 2, the compound's increased activity may be interrupted by hydrogen bonding through Tle560, Tyr555, Gly449, Glu446, His95 and Ala97 2.2, 2.01, 2.21, 3.1, 2,9 and 2.42Å separation distances, respectively, and With Ile358 and Asp357, PH4, which occupied the catalytic site entrance, are involved in π -alkyl-hydrophobic and π -anion-electrostatic bindings. And with Phe601, Asp568, and Asp469, the hydrazide functionality in PH6 mediated a number of electrostatic interactions, such as π -cation, and salt linkage. In the interim, this compound's PH6 engaged in an N-loop π -anion electrostatic contact Asp142. Unlike PH6, the Pyridine ring of the PH6 occupied the active site pocket's entrance and created a hydrophobic barrier through interactions with Asn-411, Phe415, and Arg386 that were π - π T-shaped, π -alkyl, and π - σ , respectively. In the N-loop, PH6's pyridine ring and Ala-344 established a π - σ hydrophobic contact. In the meantime, this compound's hydrazide moiety generated salt bridges with the catalytic residue Asp412 and Asp321 in the N-loop. Depicted in Figure 5(E)

4.4. Interaction of PH9 with NS5B: The Pyridinyl-hydrazide derivative PH9 was selected to examine the binding capability to inhibit hepatitis-C virus (HCV) NS5B polymerase. It is conclude from molecular docking results that ligand PH9 exhibit good inhibition to NS5B polymerase with an interacting affinity of -10.62

kcal/mol and inhibition constant of 16.29 nanomolar, as shown in the table, PH9 demonstrated excellent inhibition of the NS5B enzyme. The aforementioned chemical was designed to fill the auxiliary pocket that the NS5B active site generated. Compound PH9 interacted with the enzyme's active residues, which are nearly necessary for its inhibitory action. According to Table 2, the compound's increased activity may be interrupted by hydrogen bonding through Ser368 and Arg200, 3.24, 3.1Å separation distances, respectively, and with His245 and Ile376, PH9, which occupied the catalytic site entrance, are involved in π -alkyl-hydrophobic and π -anion-electrostatic bindings. And with His354, Val558, and Asn259, the hydrazide functionality in PH9 mediated a number of electrostatic interactions, such as π -cation, and salt linkage. In the interim, this compound's PH9 engaged in an N-loop π -anion electrostatic contact His290. The Pyridine ring of the PH9 occupied the active site pocket's entrance and created a hydrophobic barrier through interactions with Cys366, Leu384, and Arg386 that were π - π T-shaped, π -alkyl, and π - σ , respectively. In the N-loop, PH9's pyridine ring and Lue234 established a π - σ hydrophobic contact. In the meantime, this compound's hydrazide moiety generated salt bridges with the catalytic residue His376 and Asp321 in the N-loop. Depicted in Figure 6 (E)

Table 2. Residues involved in interactions and their distances of selected compounds with NS5B

Compounds	Interacting amino acids	Types of interactions	Distances(Å)
PH1	Asn141, Ala16, Ser39	H-Bonding,	2.1, 2.2, 2.0
	Glu17, Ser39, Ser407, Thr403, Arg394, Glu143	π - π interaction, Halogen (Florine) interaction	3.2, 3.7
PH2	Asn142, Glu18, Ser39	H-Bonding	2.2, 3.1, 2.4
	Phe193, Gly410, Phe551, Gly449, Cys366, Glu446, Ile447	π - π interaction, Halogen (Florine) interaction	3.2, 3.7, 3.62
PH6	Tle560, Tyr555, Gly449	H-Bonding	2.2, 2.01, 2.21, 3.1, 2.9
	Glu446, His95, Glu17, Asn-411, Phe415, Arg386, Gly283,	π - π interaction, Halogen (Florine) interaction	3.2, 3.7, 3.5, 4.2

PH9	Gly557Glu446		
	Ser368, Arg200, Cys366, Leu384, and Arg386, Thr403, Arg394, Glu143	H-Bonding π - π interaction, Halogen (Florine) interaction	3.24, 3.1 3.7, 3.2

Figure-3: Binding poses of PH1 with NS5B, (A) complex, (B) 3D interactions, (C) H-bonding, (D) hydrophobic bonding, and (E) 2Dinteractions.

Figure-4: Binding poses of PH2 with NS5B, (A) complex, (B) 3D interactions, (C) H-bonding, (D) hydrophobic bonding, and (E) 2Dinteractions.

Figure-5: Binding poses of PH6 with NS5B, (A) complex, (B) 3D interactions, (C) H-bonding, (D) hydrophobic bonding, and € 2Dinteractions.

Figure-6: Binding poses of PH9 with NS5B, (A) complex, (B) 3D interactions, (C) H-bonding, (D) hydrophobic bonding, and € 2Dinteractions

Conclusion:

It was found from the result of docking analysis that tested compounds from PH1-PH12 displayed good inhibitory activity against NS5B polymerase with respective binding energies of -8.87 to -10.62 in kcal/mol (Table 1) compared to the reference drug guanosine-5'-triphosphate having a binding energy of

-13.82 kcal/mol [21, 22] Among them, compound PH1 was found to be the most potent and effective derivative overall the tested compounds and show strong inhibition against NS5B having binding energy of -10.67 kcal/mol, on the other hand the compound PH12 exhibited lower activity and least effective having binding energy of -8.87 kcal/mol.

These inhibitors have strong binding energies, which indicate that they can successfully reduce the activity of NS5B, making those excellent candidates for the development of novel treatments. According to the results, our title compounds PH1–PH12 exhibit better inhibitory activity against a selected receptor and may serve as a model for future design, synthesis, and optimization efforts to create more potent and selective NS5B inhibitors that are also more anticancer analogous and have fewer side effects

REFERENCES

1. Organization, W.H., *Global hepatitis report 2024: action for access in low-and middle-income countries*. 2024: World Health Organization.
2. Mooneyhan, E., et al., *Hepatitis C prevalence and elimination planning in Pakistan, a bottom-up approach accounting for provincial variation*. *Journal of viral hepatitis*, 2023. **30**(4): p. 345-354.
3. Urvashi, et al., *Development of azaindole-based frameworks as potential antiviral agents and their future perspectives*. *Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, 2022. **65**(9): p. 6454-6495.
4. Ahmad, G., et al., *N-Heterocycles as promising antiviral agents: a comprehensive overview*. *Molecules*, 2024. **29**(10): p. 2232.
5. Khan, F.A., et al., *Designing functionally substituted pyridine-Carbohydrazides for potent antibacterial and Devouring Antifungal effect on Multidrug Resistant (MDR) Strains*. *Molecules*, 2022. **28**(1): p. 212.
6. Naeem, S., et al., *An In-silico Comparative Study of Binding Affinities and Binding Orientations of Isoniazid Synthetic Analogues to InhA by AutoDock and AutoDock Vina*. *RADS Journal of Pharmacy and Allied Health Sciences*, 2024. **2**(2): p. 27-37.
7. Al-Farraj, E.S., et al., *Synthesis, Structural Determination, DFT Calculation and Biological Evaluation Supported by Molecular Docking Approach of Some New Complexes Incorporating (E)-N'-(3, 5-di-Tert-Butyl-2-Hydroxybenzylidene) Isonicotino Hydrazide Ligand*. *Applied Organometallic Chemistry*, 2025. **39**(1): p. e7768.
8. Paul, D., V. Madan, and R. Bartenschlager, *Hepatitis C virus RNA replication and assembly: living on the fat of the land*. *Cell host & microbe*, 2014. **16**(5): p. 569-579.
9. Irfan, A., et al., *An Exploration of the Inhibitory Mechanism of Rationally Screened Benzofuran-1, 3, 4-Oxadiazoles and-1, 2, 4-Triazoles as Inhibitors of NS5B RdRp Hepatitis C Virus through Pharmacoinformatic Approaches*. *Biomedicines*, 2023. **11**(11): p. 3085.
10. De Clercq, E., *Current race in the development of DAAs (direct-acting antivirals) against HCV*. *Biochemical pharmacology*, 2014. **89**(4): p. 441-452.
11. Mufti, I.U., et al., *Computer-aided identification of dengue virus NS2B/NS3 protease inhibitors: an integrated molecular modelling approach for screening of phytochemicals*. *Journal of Biomolecular Structure and Dynamics*, 2024. **42**(20): p. 11052-11063.
12. Trott, O. and A.J. Olson, *AutoDock Vina: improving the speed and accuracy of docking with a new scoring function, efficient optimization, and multithreading*. *Journal of computational chemistry*, 2010. **31**(2): p. 455-461.
13. Rashid, M., et al., *The combination of multi-approach studies to explore the potential therapeutic mechanisms of imidazole derivatives as an MCF-7 inhibitor in therapeutic strategies*. *J Frontiers in Chemistry*, 2023. **11**.
14. Ravelliani, A., et al., *Study Of Molecular Docking On Compounds With Potential As Anti-Inflammatory*. *J Jurnal eduhealth*, 2022. **13**(02): p. 1070-1078.
15. Rahman, D.E.A., et al., *Novel NS5B inhibitors as antiangiogenic and apoptotic agents via paracrine and autocrine cascades: Design, synthesis, and biological evaluation*. *J Bioorganic Chemistry*, 2023: p. 106678.
16. Sawant, S., et al., *Computational assessment of select antiviral phytochemicals as potential SARS-Cov-2 main protease inhibitors: molecular dynamics guided ensemble docking and extended molecular dynamics*. *J In silico pharmacology*, 2021. **9**: p. 1-17.

17. Amirkhanov, V., et al., *Pharmacophores modeling in terms of prediction of theoretical physicochemical properties and verification by experimental correlations of carbacylamidophosphates (CAPH) and sulfanylamidophosphates (SAPH) tested as new carbonic anhydrase inhibitors*. J Mini Reviews in Medicinal Chemistry, 2019. **19**(12): p. 1015-1027.
18. Marsha Putra, S.E., T.D. Kencana Wungu, and I. Arif, *Ab-Initio Calculation of Chlorophyll-b UV-Vis Absorbance Spectra using Gaussian 09 based Density Functional Theory (DFT)*. J International Journal of Nanoelectronics Materials, 2021. **14**(1).
19. Forli, S., et al., *Computational protein–ligand docking and virtual drug screening with the AutoDock suite*. J Nature protocols, 2016. **11**(5): p. 905-919.
20. Chen, I.-J. and N. Foloppe, *Drug-like bioactive structures and conformational coverage with the LigPrep/ConfGen suite: comparison to programs MOE and catalyst*. J Journal of chemical information modeling, 2010. **50**(5): p. 822-839.
21. Zhang, X.Y., et al., *Design, synthesis and biological evaluation of oxalamide derivatives as potent neuraminidase inhibitors*. J New Journal of Chemistry, 2022. **46**(28): p. 13533-13539.
22. Eldehna, W.M., et al., *Type IIA-Type IIB protein tyrosine kinase inhibitors hybridization as an efficient approach for potent multikinase inhibitor development: Design, synthesis, anti-proliferative activity, multikinase inhibitory activity and molecular modeling of novel indolinone-based ureides and amides*. J European Journal of Medicinal Chemistry, 2019. **163**: p. 37-53.

